

IMPACT OF STARTUP INDIA POLICIES ON GROWTH OF MICRO, SMALL & MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN INDIA – A BRIEF STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The Indian economy has acknowledged the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector as its vital pillar. With approximately 31 million establishments, this sector significantly contributes to employment generation, manufacturing output, and exports. In a concerted effort to further boost local manufacturing and business, the Indian government has implemented programs like Start-up India and Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyaan (Self-Reliant India Campaign). The Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (M/o MSME) aims to cultivate a thriving MSME sector. This endeavor includes promoting the expansion and progress of the MSME Sector, which encompasses Khadi, Village, and Coir Industries. This collaborative endeavor involves partnering with pertinent Ministries/Departments, State Governments, and diverse stakeholders. The goal is to offer assistance to existing businesses and stimulate the establishment of new ones. These initiatives are designed to provide support to MSMEs and cultivate a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship within the nation. On the other hand, Start-up India represents a flagship initiative by the Government of India with the aim of establishing a robust ecosystem for nurturing innovation and Start-ups in the country. This initiative is designed to facilitate sustainable economic growth and create substantial employment opportunities. Through Start-up India, the government aspires to empower Start-ups to flourish by fostering innovation and creative design. This article will delve into the effects of these schemes on MSMEs and how they are propelling growth and innovation in India.

Keywords: Start-up India, MSMEs, Government Schemes, Atmanirbar Bharat Abhiyaan.

INTRODUCTION

The MSME sector holds a critical position in India's economic advancement. It contributes roughly 45% to manufacturing output and approximately 40% to exports. With a vast network comprising 31 million units, this sector provides employment to over 70 million individuals. Engaged in various domains, from traditional industries to advanced sectors like auto components, leather goods, textiles, engineering items, and pharmaceuticals.

However, despite making significant economic contributions, MSMEs face challenges such as limited market access, capital constraints, and difficulties in scaling up operations. Acknowledging the sector's potential, the Indian government has implemented various programs and policies to strengthen and empower MSMEs in their path to growth.

Start-up India: Fostering Innovation and Entrepreneurship

In response to the burgeoning number of new businesses and first-generation entrepreneurs in 2014, the government launched the Start-up India initiative. This flagship program seeks to cultivate a robust ecosystem conducive to nurturing innovation and Start-ups in the nation. It concentrates on empowering Start-ups to expand through innovation and design, thus promoting sustainable economic growth and fostering job creation.

The Start-up India initiative offers a range of benefits to eligible Start-ups, including tax exemptions, access to funding, simplified compliance procedures, and support for intellectual property rights. Startups refer to organizations incorporated or registered in India within the last five years, with an annual turnover not surpassing INR 25 crore. These entities concentrate on innovation, development, deployment, or commercialization of new products, processes, or services propelled by technology or intellectual property.

Government Schemes for MSMEs

Aside from the Start-up India initiative, the Indian government has introduced several schemes and programs specifically aimed at MSMEs. These endeavors strive to enhance the competitiveness of MSMEs, provide financial assistance, foster innovation, and improve the overall business environment for MSMEs in the country. Some key schemes include:

1. Prime Minister Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP)
2. Credit Guarantee Trust Fund for Micro & Small Enterprises (CGTMSE)

3. Interest Subsidy Eligibility Certificate (ISEC)
4. Market Promotion & Development Scheme (MPDA)
5. Technology Up gradation and Quality Certification
6. National Manufacturing Competitiveness Programme (NMCP)

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Rajroop Singh Chahal and Abhishek Chahal (2023) opined that Indian entrepreneurs succeed due to extensive assistance given by the India Government. Other than the central government, some state governments are offering their full support for modifying their laws and expanding the plans to facilitate commerce. Recent government statistics indicate a significant surge in the number of registered Start-ups within the nation, escalating from 452 in 2016 to an estimated 84,012 by November 30, 2022. Furthermore, the data highlights India's notably higher success rate for Start-ups in comparison to other countries. Positioned as the third-largest Start-up ecosystem globally, following the United States and China, India continues to demonstrate its robust entrepreneurial landscape. As forecasted by Stride One, a tech-enabled NBFC, Start-ups are anticipated to elevate their contribution to India's GDP from the current 2.5-3% to approximately 4-5% over the next three to five years. The Indian economy, characterized by entrepreneurship grounded in innovation, remains one of the world's fastest-growing economies.

Dr. Kuldeep Kumar (2023) in his paper attempted to clarify the role of Start-up India schemes how they are contributing to the development on the Indian economy. India ranked third placed behind United States and United Kingdom. It is expected that India will cross 50000 Start-up units per year by 2025, for the year 2022 it is at 26,546 Start-ups. India has to boost its own billion dollar club. Start-ups like zomato, swiggy, Groww, Ola, Meesho etc., Mobikwik, a Fintech company hopes to enter into the unicorn club by raising with another \$100 million in fundraising. Start-ups created around 65,000 new jobs in 2014 and the number is projected to reach 2,50,000 by 2021. This is only happened due to involvement of private sector, from author perception if the government succeeds in creating a pro-active Start-up environment, and then there is a lot of scope for creation of new jobs in India. This will happen, if the

investors have confidence on the people around them and trust that they will run their business in a right way.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present research study has the following Specific objectives:

1. To study the Start-up India schemes available for the development of MSMEs.
2. To study the impact of Start-up India schemes on MSMEs.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

This present research study on Impact of Start-up India Schemes on MSMEs in India is purely based on secondary data. Data has been gathered from diverse sources, including government websites associated with the Stand-up India Scheme, various research papers, and articles, all centering on the Stand-up India Scheme.

START-UP INDIA SCHEMES FOR MSMEs IN INDIA:

- 1. RAW MATERIAL ASSISTANCE SCHEME:** The Raw Material Assistance (RMA) Scheme, initiated by the Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSME) in India, aims to offer financial aid to small and medium enterprises (SMEs) for the purchase of raw materials at subsidized rates. This aid is designed to help these enterprises sustain their production and retain competitiveness in the market. Through the Raw Material Assistance Scheme, eligible SMEs can access support for acquiring raw materials, ensuring the continuous manufacturing of goods and services. By facilitating the availability of cost-effective raw materials, the scheme endeavors to improve the overall efficiency and competitive edge of the participating enterprises. Moreover, it contributes to the advancement and progress of the MSME sector, which holds a pivotal position in the Indian economy.

Benefits of this scheme:

- a. Facilitating the purchase of raw materials by providing credit support for a period of 180 days,
- b. Thereby assisting SMEs in accessing cost-saving benefits such as bulk purchases and cash discounts.

2. **ASPIRE - A SCHEME FOR PROMOTION OF INNOVATION, RURAL INDUSTRIES AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP:** The Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSME) in India strives to encourage entrepreneurship, innovation, and the growth of rural industries through the introduction of the ASPIRE (A Scheme for Promotion of Innovation, Rural Industries, and Entrepreneurship) scheme. From this scheme, various forms of support are provided to micro and small enterprises to encourage the growth in rural areas. It's mainly focuses on creating a conducive ecosystem for promoting and nurturing entrepreneurship in rural regions. By encouraging innovation and the uptake of cutting-edge technologies, the program strives to bolster the competitiveness of rural enterprises and guarantee their enduring progress.

With the implementation of the ASPIRE scheme, the government is committed to generating employment prospects, revitalizing rural economies, and cultivating a climate of ingenuity and entrepreneurial spirit in rural communities. Ultimately, this initiative contributes to the comprehensive economic advancement and progress of the nation.

3. **ENTREPRENEURIAL AND MANAGERIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SMES THROUGH INCUBATORS:** Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSME) in India, initiatives launched a program called 'Entrepreneurial and Managerial Development of SMEs through Incubators' (EMDI) scheme. The primary objective of this scheme is to promote the growth and development of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) by providing them with the necessary guidance and support to strengthen their managerial and entrepreneurial capabilities.

This EMDI scheme aims to enhance the overall competitiveness of SMEs by equipping them with the requisite skills and knowledge in areas such as business planning, market research, financial management, and technology adoption. By facilitating the development of a robust entrepreneurial ecosystem, the EMDI scheme contributes to the creation of a vibrant and sustainable SME sector in the country.

Benefits under this scheme:

Financial assistance for the establishment of 'Business Incubators (BI)' can range from Rs 4 to 8 lakh for each incubate/idea, with an overall ceiling of Rs 62.5 lakh for each BI.

- For Up gradation of infrastructure: Rs 2.50 lakh.

- For Orientation/training: Rs 1.28 lakh.
- For Administrative expenses: Rs 0.22 lakh.

4. SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (S&T) FOR COIR INSTITUTIONS SCHEME:

The Science and Technology (S&T) for Coir Institutions scheme is a program that focuses on promoting the implementation of scientific and technological progress in the coir industry. Its primary objective is to elevate the productivity, efficiency, and competitiveness of coir institutions by incorporating contemporary scientific and technological methodologies into their functioning. The scheme offers assistance and resources to coir institutions, enabling them to embrace pioneering approaches, enhance product excellence, and streamline production procedures.

The Key components of the Science and Technology(S&T) for Coir Institutions scheme may include the following:

- a. Supporting Research and Development (R&D): Providing financial assistance for research endeavours focused on creating new technologies, products, and processes beneficial to the coir industry.
- b. Facilitating Technology Up gradation: Offering resources and guidance to support coir institutions in upgrading their machinery, equipment, and production methods in line with the latest technological advancements in their field.
- c. Conducting Training and Skill Development: Organizing workshops and training programs to enhance the technical skills and knowledge of workers and artisans in the coir industry, thereby improving their efficiency and expertise.
- d. Assisting with Quality Certification: Helping coir institutions acquire quality certifications and standards to ensure the production of high-quality coir products that meets both national and international standards.
- e. Promoting Innovation: Encouraging coir institutions to adopt innovative practices and technologies that can lead to the development of new and improved coir products, thus expanding their market potential and competitiveness.

The government endeavors to bolster the coir industry, foster sustainable development, and establish it as a globally competitive sector in the domain of natural fibers and associated products.

5. **TRADE RELATED ENTREPRENEURSHIP ASSISTANCE AND DEVELOPMENT (TREAD) SCHEME FOR WOMEN:** The Trade Related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development (TREAD) Scheme for women is an initiative in India, dedicated to empower women entrepreneurs with a particular focus on those who are from economically weaker sections to establish and develop their small-scale businesses. This program seeks to bolster women's economic empowerment by extending financial support, training, and vital resources, thereby fostering their active engagement in entrepreneurial endeavors.

Benefits under this scheme:

Assistance is provided in the form of a Government of India (GoI) grant amounting to 30 percent of the overall project cost. Additionally, eligible training institutions and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) conducting training programs for the empowerment of women beneficiaries identified under this scheme can access a GoI grant of up to Rs. 1.00 lakh per program.

CLASSIFICATION OF MSMEs

The classification of MSMEs was classified based on the Investment on Plant & Machinery/Equipment and Annual Turnover, namely:

Revised MSME Classification – Composite Criterion

CATEGORY	Investment in Plant & Machinery/Equipment	Annual Turnover
MICRO	Not More Than 1 Crore	Not More Than 5 Crores
SMALL	Not More Than 10 Crores	Not More Than 50 Crores
MEDIUM	Not More Than 50 Crores	Not More Than 250 Crores

Source: Annual Reports.

Distribution of Enterprises - Category Wise

Sector	Micro	Small	Medium	Total
Rural	3,24,09,000	78,000	1000	3,24,88,000
Urban	3,06,43,000	2,53,000	4000	3,09,00,000
All	6,30,52,000	3,31,000	5000	6,33,88,000

Source: Annual Reports.

Comparative Analysis: The comparative distribution of MSMEs in the Top 10 states were given below:

Sl. No.	State/UT	NSS 73 rd round*		Fourth All India Census of MSME and Fifth Economic Census**	
		Number	Share (%)	Number	Share (%)
1.	Uttar Pradesh	89,99,000	14	44,03,000	12
2.	West Bengal	88,67,000	14	34,64,000	10
3.	Tamil Nadu	49,48,000	8	33,13,000	9
4.	Maharashtra	47,78,000	8	30,63,000	8
5.	Karnataka	38,34,000	6	20,19,000	6
6.	Bihar	34,46,000	5	14,70,000	4
7.	Andhra Pradesh***	33,87,000	5	25,96,000	7
8.	Gujarat	33,16,000	5	21,78,000	6
9.	Rajasthan	26,87,000	4	16,64,000	5
10.	Madhya Pradesh	26,74,000	4	19,33,000	5
11.	Total of above Ten States	4,69,40,000	74	2,61,04,000	72
12.	Other States/UTs	1,64,50,000	26	1,00,72,000	28
13.	All	6,33,90,000	100	3,61,76,000	100

* NSS 73rd Round, 2015-16.

** Fourth All India Census of MSME, 2006-07 (Unregistered Sector) and Fifth Economic Census.

*** including Telangana in Fourth All India Census of MSME.

IMPACT OF START-UP INDIA ON MSMEs

The Start-up India initiative has positively influenced MSMEs in India. It has created an environment conducive to innovation and entrepreneurship, encouraging MSMEs to explore new avenues and embrace technological advancements. The initiative has provided a platform for MSMEs to connect with investors, mentors, and industry experts, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Under the Start-up India program, the government has introduced tax exemptions for Start-ups, providing much-needed financial impetus. Start-ups can avail income tax exemption for three years within a block of five years if they are incorporated between April 1, 2016, and

March 31, 2019. Additionally, investments made in Start-ups above fair market value are also exempt from tax.

To strengthen Start-ups even more, the government has set up a 'fund of funds' with a fund size of INR 10,000 Crores, overseen by the Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI). This fund invests in SEBI registered Alternative Investment Funds (AIFs), and these funds, in turn, make investments in Start-ups. The fund acts as a catalyst in attracting private capital for Start-ups, aiding in their scaling up endeavors.

Some of the notable effects include:

Encouraging innovation: These initiatives have nurtured an environment of innovation within the MSME sector, inspiring entrepreneurs to explore novel concepts and technologies.

- i. **Access to funds:** MSMEs have experienced enhanced access to funding through various financial incentives and support provided by the Start-up India program, facilitating the expansion of their operations.
- ii. **Simplified compliance procedures:** The simplification of regulatory processes has alleviated the bureaucratic burden on MSMEs, allowing them to dedicate more attention to their business activities and expansion.
- iii. **Enhanced visibility:** Through diverse networking events and programs, MSMEs have enjoyed heightened visibility and exposure, facilitating connections with potential investors, partners, and customers.
- iv. **Skill enhancement:** This scheme has facilitated workshops, and skill development programs equipping MSMEs with the necessary expertise and knowledge to compete effectively in the contemporary market.
- v. **Boosting exports:** By fostering innovation and creating a conducive environment for Start-ups, the schemes have contributed to the escalation of exports from the MSME sector, thereby bolstering the nation's economy.

In summary, the Start-up India schemes have played a pivotal role in cultivating a supportive ecosystem for MSMEs, enabling them to flourish, innovate, and make significant contributions to the Indian economy.

CONCLUSION

The Start-up India schemes and government initiatives have had a positive impact on MSMEs in India. They have created an ecosystem that encourages innovation, entrepreneurship, and growth. By providing financial support, tax exemptions, and access to funding, these initiatives have empowered MSMEs and Start-ups to scale up their operations and contribute to the country's economic growth. However, there is still work to be done in terms of addressing the challenges faced by MSMEs and ensuring a conducive business environment for their sustained growth. With continued efforts, collaboration, and support, MSMEs and Start-ups in India have the potential to drive innovation, employment generation, and economic development in the years to come.

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